

CLIMATIC CHANGES AND CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE ROLE OF FSE IN THE STORM PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

The EU H2020 research project STORM is aimed at improving the safety of cultural heritage against the hazards deriving from climatic changes. Damages caused directly by forest fires or by fires fostered by heat waves will be more frequent in the future. The corresponding risks will have to be addressed with appropriate tools and fire safety engineering approach is the best tool to combine safety needs with those of economic and organisational efficiency nature. Increasing average air temperatures and moisture will change the fire spread, both in confined environments and in non-confined scenarios. This new situation will bring also to the need of integrating the outcomes of forest fires simulation tools with the input data of the classic fire safety engineering models.

Fire safety engineering approach will allow also to define the appropriate combination of human resources, training activities and physical features needed in the future scenarios in managing emergency, helping to define the most cost-effective solutions.

1. INTRODUCTION

STORM (Safeguarding Cultural Heritage through Technical and Organisational Resources Management) is a Horizon 2020 research project financed in 2016 by the European Commission under the Disaster Resilience & Climate Change Topic 3: “*Mitigating the impacts of climate change and natural hazards on Cultural Heritage sites, structures and artefacts*”. The project plans to introduce an integrated framework and a platform providing tools and services both at macro level to give a global view of the entire value chain and at specific level to promote the improvement of specific processes for protection and prevention. Among the other objectives, the project aims at giving stakeholders the possibility to improve existing processes related to three identified areas: Prevention, Intervention and Policies, planning and processes (figure 1). Since climatic changes will

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bring new risks and will worsen the existing ones to the cultural heritage buildings, fire safety is one of the main areas of interest.

The grow of average temperatures, the possibility of heat waves and the risk of drought in large areas that have not experienced such situations yet, predictably will affect the current basis of fire risk assessment, obliging fire engineers and stakeholders in general, to consider the need of new specific protective measures, as well as management of emergency solutions.

Fig. 1. STORM Project overall tasks.

In the new context, the current fire safety approach, which is based on an extensive use of prescriptive rules [1], could reveal to not be the most effective, both for safety purposes and for economical considerations. On the other hand, it is widely accepted that one of the main roles of discipline defined as fire safety engineering [2] is referred to the limitation of the costs of the safety features and to the improvement of the management efficiency. On such basis, the first problem that fire safety engineers have to deal with is the definition of fire scenarios and of input data necessary to the simulations when it comes to apply ordinary scenarios to particularly sensitive materials as the historic ones. Moreover, the new threats related to climatic changes will oblige to fire scenarios with an higher probability of occurrence of conditions (average high air temperatures, low humidity) that at the moment are considered as rare events. Normally, higher environmental initial temperatures imply a faster fire spread inside buildings. Also in wild land urban interface (the zone of transition between unoccupied land and human development) fires that can endanger historic or cultural buildings, drier conditions will contribute to an increased probability of ignition and to a faster spread. As a consequence, the production of firebrands will bring new risks to be considered in the fire scenarios of both confined and open environments.

2. THE EFFECTS OF CLIMATIC CHANGE ON FIRE SAFETY OF CULTURAL HERITAGE

2.1. Main effects of climatic change and the risk of fire

The effects of the climate changes, their nature and origin are being studied, some results have been delivered. An analysis funded by the EU [3] shows some data of interest for the purposes of this paper. In particular, compared to the preindustrial level (end of the 19th century), the mean

temperature and the frequency and length of heat waves have increased across Europe. Among the main observed effects, there is the increase in the frequency and intensity of droughts (in particular in southern Europe), the growing of the number of forest fires in the Mediterranean region between 1980 and 2000 and a decrease thereafter and the increased demand for cooling (particularly in southern Europe). On such specific issue the Authors note that the decrease of number of fires has to be quoted together with the burnt areas of the fires, which seems to be increasing.

Two effects can be highlighted in analysing possible growing fire risk to cultural heritage buildings and artefacts: higher environmental temperature, related to a faster fire spread inside and outside heritage and historic buildings, and the worsened role of forest fires as ignition cause of buildings fires.

2.2. Impact of climatic change on fire spread within confined environments

Under the Author's point of view, the concern related to increased average temperatures and particularly severe heat waves can be treated only with the fire safety engineering approach, due to the complexity of the response to threat, which depends on the specific fire behaviour of each single material to be protected. It is widely known that fire spread is largely conditioned by the initial set that describe the environment and the burning objects [4]. But what will be the effect on the objects to protect if average initial temperature will be up to 30 °C instead of the 20 °C normally considered is not known. Normally this consideration is not significant when it comes to assess ordinary material protection, but historical and cultural heritage materials in many cases are particularly sensitive to small variations of parameters like temperature, humidity, wave length of light and IR radiations, so it makes sense to take a deeper look at this issue.

Fig. 2. Map of predicted climate change in Europe. Image adapted From [3]

2.3. Impact of climatic change on fire spread in WUI scenarios

In fire disciplines, Wildland Urban Interface (WUI) refers to the zone of transition between unoccupied land and human development. The safety problem of Cultural Heritage in this case can be related to the forest fires indicator (which monitors the areas burnt by forest fires, experienced in many European countries, in particular in southern Europe). The study quoted above considers that

the change “*may lead to more forest fires due to warmer and drier weather, and possibly increases in lightning storms (a natural cause of fires)*”. Applying this consideration to the risk of ignition to heritage buildings and artefacts caused by flaming parts of wild land burning near cultural heritage sites could lead to the necessity of studying with the fire safety engineering approach a new set of fire scenarios, where higher air temperatures and low environmental humidity are coupled with a number of possible fire triggers brought by the wind. Assessing the severity of such new risks means using the traditional fire safety engineering approach and the forest fire simulation tools as source of data. It can be interesting noting that such situation (historic or cultural building exposed to external fire threat) has been treated in the NFPA standard on Historic Structures [5] within a specific scenario related to the exposure to an external fire. It refers, in particular, to a fire that begins in a distant area from the area that has to be evaluated and that propagates in the area or that blocks escape routes or makes its internal conditions unsustainable.

3. FIRE SAFETY ENGINEERING AND THE RESPONSE TO THE NEW THREATS

3.1. The STORM approach to the management of the new risks

STORM project deals with a lot of new or more severe hazards caused by the climatic change to which Cultural heritage is exposed. It does not only treats fire but also drought, floods, and other situations that can worsen Cultural heritage conservation. The fundamental response proposed by the project is creating an engineered approach, that allows stakeholders to access to the most appropriate information in the planning of safety, management of emergency and recovery phases. Such approach brings directly, when it is possible, to use simulation tools to improve situation awareness (both before and during the emergency) to adopt the most appropriate actions. In the case of fire risks, the STORM approach implies the use of an engineered path that, both in confined environments fires and in urban wild land fires, could lead the stakeholders from the risk assessment to the choice of safety and management action based on facts and numbers.

3.2. Fire risks in confined environments

Fire growth process in confined environments has been widely studied and, in the last 20 and more years, a number of models and software have been developed to help assessing the risks associated to the speed of heat and smoke production [6]. Unfortunately, the large amount of studies produced only seldom have addressed the problem of the risks associated with the exposition of cultural heritage materials to the fire [7], [8]. So, also the aspect of considering an environmental temperature higher than the average but within the range predicted for the future has been normally neglected. Its effect, in fact, isn't normally important when ordinary buildings have to be assessed, but the lack of data does not allow researchers and engineers to be sure about its irrelevance when cultural heritage materials are threatened by fire effluents. The simulations have been performed using Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) that is a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model of fire-driven fluid flow. [9] The software solves numerically a form of the Navier-Stokes equations appropriate for low-speed, thermally-driven flow, with an emphasis on smoke and heat transport from fires. Smoke View (SMV) is a visualization program that is used to display the output of FDS simulations. FDS is free software developed by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) of the United States Department of Commerce. For this project, the simulation domain and input parameters were selected using an example model from NIST FDS dataset called Room Fire. For our purpose, the only parameter modified was the initial temperature (TMPA) from 20°C to 35°C. In Fig. 3 and 4 the results of a simulation performed in a simple environment with a difference of initial air temperature of 15 °C show an increase of growth of temperature and heat rate release of the fire effluents that could be extremely significant to assess the compatibility of the condition with the preservation of historic materials, even if it is normally negligible in assessing ordinary buildings safety. A possible response to the enhanced fire risks to cultural heritage caused by climatic change should start from the FSE

approach. The results of the simulation, in fact, could be used to choose the most appropriate measures to prevent and limit damages. A novel use of such simulations could be identified in assisting the management of emergencies. Giving the emergency managers the possibility of deciding on the basis of reliable data which is the best strategy to limit damages to cultural heritage during a fire is already feasible. Information technologies can provide, and in some cases already do provide, such kind of contribution to the situation awareness.

Fig. 3. Comparison between simulated temperature-time curves with different initial air temperature

Fig. 4. Comparison between simulated HRR curves with different initial air temperature

3.3. Fire risks in open environments

The problem of more severe environmental fire risks to cultural heritage due to climatic changes can be summarized under two aspects: how the external events will affect indoor environmental quality,

either through increases in airborne contaminant levels or challenges in maintaining acceptable indoor environmental conditions, and the increased risk of triggering fire to buildings in case of external wild land fires. The first case [10], is directly connected to the issues briefly described in the previous section: gases and smokes due to external combustions can damage historic artefacts just like the same products do when generated by a fire inside buildings. Again, cultural heritage problems hasn't been deeply studied until now by the FSE as normal targets of the analysis do not have so low sensitivity thresholds. Even the second case, increased probability of buildings fires caused by WUI fires, will need appropriate scenarios and new uses of the simulation tools to represent appropriately the mechanism of triggering a building fire starting from firebrands. In this regard it should be considered that in the literature there are many publications which describe the models of generation and transport of hot particles. A review can be found in [11].

Fig. 4. left) Vertical profiles of (a) central vertical plume velocity up and (b) minimum loftable height z_0 as functions of particle size d_p . From [12]; right) Photograph of a burning douglas-fir tree (5.2 m) used for firebrand. collection From [13]

4. DISCUSSION

Cultural heritage is an extremely wide concept, whose extension is continuing growing. The fire behaviour of materials that contribute to make tangible an artefact, a building or any other object of historical or cultural value hasn't been studied until now, except a very limited and not adequate number of exceptions. As a consequence, the community which will have to protect such heritage against the effects of climatic change will have to define which of such effects will affect fire safety and accordingly assess in which extension the risks will grow. Two main areas of knowledge will be involved: the effect of the change on environment and the behaviour of historic materials in case of fire. The impact of climatic change on such specific group of materials should be assessed quantitatively to understand if the threat needs to open a new area of research about fire behaviour of historic materials.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The main problem that, at the moment, fire engineers face when they have to assess fire safety of historic fabrics and construction materials is the lack of adequate data on fire behavior of such objects and their response to extinguishing agents. Ignoring performance criteria means the practical impossibility to adopt the FSE approach and, thus, giving up using the most efficient way to pursue the preservation goals in case of fire.

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